

PROOFS REVIEW CHECKLIST

Paper Title: _____

Proofs Due: _____

Before beginning

- Email co-authors soliciting comments, including intended date of proofs submission
- Copy printed in color, with references section separate from main body of paper
- Three highlighters, with separate colors for:
 - Citations/references _____
 - Quotations _____
 - Figures and tables _____
- One black pen for comments and one red pen for corrections

Front matter

- Title is spelled correctly and makes sense
- Keywords are spelled correctly and make sense
- Author name and affiliation correct
- Corresponding email address correct
- Co-author names and affiliations / corresponding information correct
- Read abstract for sense and copy-edits
- Check running headers are spelled correctly (title, author names)

Text

- Read body text for sense and copy-edits
- Read footnotes/endnotes for sense, correspondence to numbering system, and copy-edits
- Check footnote/endnote markers are placed in the correct locations
- Check section titles for sense; and check sections are numbered sequentially
- Verify all quotations are from correct references (year, page)

Figures and tables

- All figures are cited in text sequentially and match their descriptions
- Figure captions have consistent style (periods, no periods, etc.)
- Figures print at correct resolution
- Figure captions are legible (especially axes and labels)
- All tables are cited in text sequentially and match their descriptions
- Table captions have consistent style (periods, no periods, etc.)
- Simple math in tables is correct (addition, percentages, etc.)
- All references in figures and tables are correct

References

- All in-text citations are included in references (highlighter)
- In-text citation and reference dates agree (checkmark / underline)
- In-text citation and references agree on author names (spelling, accents, hyphens)
- In-text citation order is correct (alphabetical, chronological)
- In-text citations have consistent style (commas, ampersands, semi-colons)
- All references are included as in-text citations (highlighter)
- Reference list is consistent in style
 - capitalization
 - pagination
 - journal abbreviations
 - DOIs
 - city/press order
- Read through reference list to verify content makes sense

Acknowledgements

- All contributors are acknowledged
- Contributor names are spelled correctly
- All funding bodies are listed in acknowledgements using appropriate text
- All grant numbers are correct

Final logistics

- All mark-up is transferred to word or pdf document
- Email to editor is drafted if larger changes are needed or smaller changes warrant explanation

Additional considerations

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Proofs Submitted: _____